

Background-Free Interferometric Dynamic Light Scattering

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Abstract—Heterodyne detection of dynamic light scattering (DLS) leverages the interference between light scattered by a sample and a reference field, and it is especially suited to amplify weak scattering signals. Unfortunately, the reference field used for amplification results in a strong baseline, which can mask small fluctuations and saturate the photodetector at higher gains. We introduce a novel DLS sensing architecture that integrates balanced detection into a dual-path configuration where coherence-gated (CG), common-path, fiber interferometers are introduced for interferometric amplification and background removal. In the proposed design of balanced CG-DLS, two independent reference fields arise intrinsically from the Fresnel reflection at the tip of an optical fiber in separate arms; one acts as a local oscillator for the scattered field, and the other is used for baseline removal, overall enabling the detection of interferometrically amplified scattering in a background-free manner. We provide comprehensive descriptions of the instrument's assembly and its optimization using general-purpose optical components as well as the signal processing, characterization, and information retrieval through experiments with model colloidal suspensions. Ultimately, we demonstrate the capability of balanced CG-DLS to perform particle sizing at ultralow concentrations, down to 1×10^{-7} vol/vol, where around ten nanoparticles are present in the measurement volume.

Index Terms—Dynamic light scattering (DLS), optical fiber devices, optical fibers, optical sensors, random media.

I. INTRODUCTION

LIGHT scattering from nonabsorbing nanoparticles (NPs) constitutes a rich source of information for the quantification of properties such as size, shape, charge [1], and even mass [2]. Measuring these properties has gained significant interest in recent years, driven by the exponential growth of NP-based technologies, especially in the medical field [3], [4].

In the visible range, nonabsorbing NPs have a scattering cross section, which is several orders of magnitude smaller than the geometrical one, making them scatter light inefficiently, with scattering efficiency $Q_s < 1\%$ [5]. Although this

might not be problematic at higher concentrations, measuring directly (homodyne detection) the light scattered by a particles ensemble, I_s , as it is done in dynamic light scattering (DLS) [1], requires using sensitive detectors, like photomultiplier tubes (PMTs) or avalanche photodiodes (APDs), which in general are costly, require robust, precise external modules for signal conditioning, and are sensitive to temperature and humidity variations [6]. As concentration decreases, detection of weaker scattering signals becomes challenging and non-trivial. Unfortunately, operating at ultralow volume fractions might be inevitable when the sample is inherently scarce and valuable. For instance, plant-derived extracellular nanovesicles are extraordinary therapeutic agents, but their extraction constitutes merely around $1 \times 10^{-4}\%$ of the initial biomass, and it is further reduced in subsequent processing stages [7].

Moreover, boosting I_s by deliberately increasing the intensity of the incident light, or by taking advantage of its inherent dependence on the wavelength or the optical contrast [5], is not always feasible and risks damaging the sample, particularly if it contains biological matter. Yet, due to its relatively simple implementation and straightforward information retrieval, DLS-based technology has demonstrated great potential for in situ, noninvasive measurements [8] and has been established as a gold standard for nanometric particle size measurements in liquids (ISO 22412).

Alternatively, heterodyne detection schemes exploit the interference of scattered light with a reference electric field,

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E_r , to amplify coherently the scattering signal, E_s . Commonly, this reference signal is much stronger, therefore, the scattering information is encoded in the interference term of the detected intensity, $I(t) \approx I_r + 2\sqrt{I_r I_s} \cos(\phi(t))$, where $I_{r,s} = |E_{r,s}|^2$ is the time-averaged intensity of each field, and $\phi(t)$ the time-fluctuating phase difference between the two.

Interferometric amplification of scattering signals has been realized by providing optical coherence tomography (OCT) with DLS measurement capabilities [9], [10], which offers path-length resolution and, thanks to the temporal coherence gating, enables the extraction of single scattering from optically dense environments. Along similar lines is Doppler fluctuation spectroscopy [11], which has been widely used to measure DLS from optically thick living tissues [12].

A prominent example where interferometric detection has been championed in weakly-scattering situations is interferometric scattering microscopy (iSCAT) [13], whose exquisite sensitivity permits label-free imaging of individual molecules [14]. In the basic iSCAT setup, E_r emerges from the Fresnel reflection at the bottom of the coverslip where the sample sits and recombines in free space with the light scattered from it, in a common-path geometry. Here, the problem of having a local oscillator that overwhelms the scattering signal has been mitigated, in part, by increasing I_s by operating at shorter wavelengths [15] or by actively decreasing the magnitude of I_r with custom optical components [16]. For optical sensing, a similar situation takes place in coherence-gated DLS (CG-DLS), whose all-optical-fiber implementation is based on a common path interferometer in reflection [17]. In that case, E_r emerges inherently from Fresnel reflection at the fiber-sample interface. Among its distinctive features, CG-DLS integrates low-coherence light to optically gate a picoliter-sized volume localized at the tip of an optical fiber [17], [18], which enables operating based on the premises of single scattering across a broad range of optical regimes [17], [19], [20], [21].

In interferometric detection, the challenge roots in the fact that, in many practical scenarios, the magnitude of I_s and I_r are largely unbalanced, which makes the amplified, but still weak, scattering signal to overlay on a strong background (note that I_r persists even in the absence of scattering). From a practical standpoint, the presence of such a strong background is detrimental as it can mask small fluctuations and saturate the photodetector at higher gains.

On the other hand, using balanced detection can effectively isolate weak optical signals by subtracting a secondary signal from the main one. This form of detection has allowed removing strong backgrounds in several contexts, outstandingly in OCT [22], [23] and coherent optical time-domain reflectometry (c-OTDR) [24], [25], but also in the measurement of Faraday rotations [26], nanocrystal growth monitoring [27], spectral analysis of optical frequency combs [28], and detection of light scattering by micrometer-sized aerosols in bright backgrounds [29].

Inspired by these advances, we have integrated balanced photodetection into CG-DLS together with a modification into a dual-path setup, to allow for interferometric amplification and background removal. In the novel architecture, coined as balanced CG-DLS, two independent reference signals arise

intrinsically from the Fresnel reflection at the distal end of two optical fibers; one of them is used to amplify the scattering signal, while the other one is used to remove the baseline via hardware, overall enabling the detection of interferometrically amplified scattering in a background-free manner. Our implementation makes use of general-purpose components, and it is hardware-undemanding. We provide comprehensive guidelines for the instrument's assembly and optimization as well as for signal processing, characterization, and information retrieval. Proof-of-concept experiments were performed on model colloidal suspensions, where we demonstrate the capability of balanced CG-DLS for particle sizing at ultralow concentrations, as low as 1×10^{-7} vol/vol, where around ten NPs are present in the observation volume.

II. PROPOSED IDEA

Fig. 1(a) shows conceptually the interferometric amplification of DLS, which makes use of a single reference field, and its background-free modality, proposed here, where a second reference field is used for background removal. A collection of particles is illuminated with the incident field, E_i , and a portion of the scattered field, E_s , reaches the detector. Part of the illumination can be used as a reference field, E_r , to combine it coherently with E_s for its interferometric amplification, $I(t) \approx I_r + 2\sqrt{I_r I_s} \cos(\phi(t))$. This scenario corresponds to conventional interferometric amplification, CG-DLS included. If a second reference field, E'_r , of similar magnitude to E_r , is taken to a second detector, in principle, the analog subtraction of the signals measured at the two detectors can yield only the amplified scattering signal, without a background, $I(t) \approx 2\sqrt{I_r I_s} \cos(\phi(t))$. This is the general idea of the background-free interferometric DLS proposed here.

Fig. 1(b) shows an optical fiber-based implementation of the latter form of detection, coined as balanced CG-DLS, using general-purpose components. Light from the source is split equally into two arms, wherein fiber couplers/splitters are used in reverse as circulators to take the light to the sample and then back to a balanced detector. The independent reference fields in Fig. 1(a), E_r and E'_r , originate in separate channels from the Fresnel reflection at the distal end of the optical fiber in each arm, as indicated in the inset of Fig. 1(b); E_r arises at the fiber-sample interface and serves as local oscillator for the amplification of E_s , while E'_r originates likewise in the reference arm, in the absence of scattering, and goes directly to the balanced detector for subtraction.

The basic architecture of conventional CG-DLS makes use of a single fiber coupler/splitter, which is used in reverse as a circulator and E_r emerges from the fiber-sample interface [17]. The reader may note that it is embedded into the measurement arm of this new design, as if only coupler C3 was used together with a single-channel photodetector.

Our reasoning behind using balanced detection, as shown in Fig. 1, is to achieve the analog subtraction of the strong background produced by I_r , to enable a larger dynamic range. In other words, in balanced CG-DLS, the core of the interferometric amplification of conventional CG-DLS is preserved (the amplified fluctuations still carry the coefficient $2\sqrt{I_r I_s}$), but we introduce a second arm to remove the strong background in order to make accessible the entire range of the detector's gain, without saturation. In principle, this form of balanced detection can also suppress perturbations which are common to both arms, e.g., room temperature variations or intensity

Fig. 1. Background-free interferometric DLS. (a) Conceptual representation of interferometric DLS and its proposed background-free modality. (b) Schematic of balanced CG-DLS, where the two reference fields, shown in (a), are generated in independent arms from the Fresnel reflection at the fiber-medium interface (inset); one of them amplifies the scattering signal collected from a picoliter-sized coherence volume, located at the tip of the optical fiber, while the second one allows for background removal at the balance detector.

drifts from the light source, since both I_r and I'_r would change accordingly; however, perturbations which act independently in each arm will go unsuppressed, e.g., sharp temperature gradients between arms.

In configurations of OCT [22], [23] and c-OTDR [24], [25] where balanced detection is used, a similar purpose is pursued (interferometric amplification plus background removal); however, there are major differences as compared to balanced CG-DLS. In those techniques, E_r and E_s propagate through different paths and are then mixed using a lossless 2×2 fiber coupler with a 50:50 splitting ratio before reaching the detector. By taking advantage of the intrinsic $\pi/2$ rad relative phase shift that a linear, symmetric directional coupler introduces between the two output ports [30], [31], the interference term ends up being in antiphase at the two channels of the balanced detector; in this way, the background is removed in the subtraction. The same result can be obtained with two independent detectors, as it has been demonstrated with cameras [32], line array detectors [33], spectrometers [34], and a single multi-channel spectrometer, where alternatively the phase shift was introduced with cube beam splitters [35]. In our case, on the contrary, E_r and E_s propagate together in our common path geometry; in other words, there are already mixed. Moreover, our common path geometry secures that E_r and E_s interfere regardless of the length of the optical fibers, without the need for complex setups to match their optical paths within the coherence length [34], [36], [37]. Furthermore, although the background intensity can be successfully removed in balanced

configurations of OCT and c-OTDR, care should be exerted regarding the amplitude of E_r , because the excess noise at each channel of the balanced detector is proportional to the product $I_r I_s$ [23], [36], which directly impacts the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) [33], [38]. In our case, low-amplitude reference fields are generated through Fresnel reflections, with matching intensities, which also helps in balancing the noise level in each channel of the balanced detector. One last practical advantage for the dual-path configuration of balanced CG-DLS is that the background measurement can account for scattering in the suspending medium, allowing for isolation of the contribution from dynamic scatterers in the sample under study, and it can also serve as an internal feedback to monitor changes taking place in the suspending medium of the sample through deviations from the balancing condition.

In our experimental realization, light is fed from a broadband source (BLS, Superlum model BLM-S-670-G-I-4), whose approximately Gaussian spectrum is centered at a wavelength of $\lambda_0 = 670$ nm, with a bandwidth of $\Delta\lambda = 7$ nm. Its coherence length in aqueous media ($n \approx 1.331$) is $l_c = (\sqrt{2 \ln(2)}/\pi) \lambda_0^2 / n \Delta\lambda \approx 30 \mu\text{m}$ [39]. Importantly, this light source is entirely assembled by the manufacturer, stable, and especially suited for low-noise applications. Commercially available multimode fibers (MMFs) were used (Thorlabs model M42L01, made of FG050LGA fiber, $\emptyset 50 \mu\text{m}$ core, NA = 0.22). The coherence volume, defined by l_c , and the cross section of the MMF core, is $V_c \approx 60$ pL. Three fiber couplers/splitters [labeled as C1, C2, C3 in Fig. 1(b)] with similar nominal characteristics were used (multimode, $\emptyset 50 \mu\text{m}$ core, 50:50 splitting ratio, NA = 0.22) together with a two-channel, balanced photodetector (New Focus model 2107-FC-M). For comparison, experiments were also performed with CG-DLS, using a single coupler in reverse as a circulator, and a single-channel photodetector (New Focus model 2001-FC-M).

III. RESULTS

The proposed architecture for balanced CG-DLS, Fig. 1(b), makes use of general-purpose components, which are not necessarily optimized for our wavelength of operation ($\lambda_0 = 670$ nm). Specifically, although the fiber couplers have similar nominal characteristics, their splitting ratio can deviate significantly from the 50:50 ratio designed by the manufacturer. Thus, we first characterized them. Coupler C1 has splitting ratio of 54% from port 1 (P1) to port 2 (P2), and 46% from P1 to P3; couplers C2 and C3 reported splitting ratio of 35%(P1-P2)-65%(P1-P3) and 44%(P1-P2)-56%(P1-P3), respectively. Because C1 exhibited smaller deviations, it was designated as the primary splitter to ensure that the two arms are fed evenly.

Then, to achieve the best possible configuration with the components at hand, we measured the power difference between C2 and C3 with the balanced detector, for all possible connection permutations, as summarized in Fig. 2. For each permutation (labeled from A to H), the connections between the ports of the fiber couplers are indicated in the legend; for instance, permutation A consists of connecting P2 of C1-P2 of C2, and P3 of C1-P2 of C3. Because the proposed setup is to be used mainly in aqueous samples, this characterization was carried out by keeping the fiber tip of both arms immersed in ultrapure water, in separate containers.

Fig. 2. Absolute power difference between couplers C2 and C3, for different connection permutations among the fiber couplers (C1, C2, and C3), swapping them at the channels of the balanced photodetector. The legend indicates the connections between the ports (P1, P2, and P3) of the fiber couplers. Permutation G (red arrow) was identified as the best configuration for balanced CG-DLS. See text for details.

According to the user manual of the balanced detector, it delivers the optical power difference between the channels (in mW) from the subtraction of channel 2 from channel 1, as $P_{Ch1-Ch2} = V_{out}/(R \cdot \xi)$, where V_{out} is the voltage readout (in Volts), R is the wavelength-dependent sensor's responsivity ($R = 0.26 \text{ V/mW}$, @ $\lambda = 670 \text{ nm}$), and ξ is the amplification gain factor. The two channels of the balanced detector have independent photodiodes and electronic circuits; consequently, they have slightly different performance (responsivity, dark current). In fact, by measuring the same terminal of C2 or C3 through channels 1 and 2, a different reading is obtained, always being lower in channel 2 by around $0.35 \mu\text{W}$; this is the intrinsic power reading mismatch between the channels of the balanced photodetector. Accordingly, for each permutation, the terminals of C2 and C3 were swapped at the detector (solid and shaded bars in Fig. 2) to clearly identify, from all possibilities, the connection permutations, which are more favorable for overall balancing. As shown in Fig. 2, permutation G successfully minimized the power difference between the channels' readout practically to the level of the intrinsic channel mismatch. Based on these results, this permutation was selected as the best balancing configuration.

After assembling the instrument, we performed proof-of-concept experiments with model colloidal suspensions to analyze the characteristics of the signals measured with balanced CG-DLS and verify that particles' dynamic information is preserved. The samples consisted of aqueous suspensions, prepared by diluting a commercial size standard (Merck model 90517, polystyrene (PS) NPs, 100 nm diameter) with high-purity, double-distilled water (Mili-Q), with particles concentration in the range from 10^{-7} to 10^{-4} vol/vol. For validation and comparison, we also performed measurements with CG-DLS and two commercial DLS instruments from two different brands (Malvern Zetasizer Nano ZS ZEN5600 and Anton Paar Litesizer DLS 700).

First, we analyzed the fluctuating part of $I(t)$ for signals acquired with both CG-DLS and balanced CG-DLS. We calculated $\delta I(t) = (I(t) - \bar{I})/\bar{I}$, which are the intensity fluctuations normalized to the signal's temporal average, \bar{I} , as shown in Fig. 3(a)–(d); $\delta I(t)$ is a metric of the fluctuations contrast which, ideally, are produced solely due to the scattering from the particles. For a fair comparison between both setups, we adjusted the intensity level of the light source to ensure that the same power was delivered to the sample (see

Fig. 3. Temporal and spectral performance of CG-DLS and balanced CG-DLS for different particle concentrations. (a)–(d) Normalized time-fluctuating intensity, $\delta I(t)$ and (e)–(h) its corresponding power spectrum, $P(f)$. Blue curves indicate measurements with CG-DLS at the maximum allowable gain ($\xi = 1 \times 10^4$); green and red curves correspond to measurements with balanced CG-DLS, at $\xi = 1 \times 10^4$ and $\xi = 3 \times 10^4$, respectively, gray curves are measurements of background noise. See text for details.

Appendix); in other words, we secured that the magnitude of the incident light, and consequently that of I_r and I_s , are kept constant.

Data were acquired at a sampling frequency of $f_s = 50 \text{ kHz}$ during $T_t = 50 \text{ ms}$, as shown in Fig. 3(a)–(d). In CG-DLS, the largest allowable gain factor was $\xi = 1 \times 10^4$ (blue curves), while balanced CG-DLS permitted using $\xi = 1 \times 10^4$ (green curves) and $\xi = 3 \times 10^4$ (red curves), which is the maximum detector's gain, without saturation. Background measurements in water were also taken for reference (gray curves).

For all concentrations, $\delta I(t)$ exhibits larger amplitude in balanced CG-DLS as compared to CG-DLS, reporting a significant overall enhancement of $\delta I(t)$ of around 75%. Notably, at the lowest concentration, Fig. 3(d), where there are approximately ten particles within the coherence volume, CG-DLS falls to the background level, while balanced CG-DLS still produces distinguishable scattering fluctuations.

After assessing the characteristics of the raw signals, we analyzed their dynamic information content, which in DLS is typically done based on the intensity autocorrelation function, $g^{(2)}(\tau)$ [1]. At the ultralow concentrations considered here, care should be exerted because $g^{(2)}(\tau)$ must account for the effects of particle number fluctuations (PNFs) [40]. Following well-known approximations that the illumination consists of a Gaussian beam with finite transverse extent, $g^{(2)}(\tau)$ is expressed as [41], [42]

$$g^{(2)}(\tau) = 1 + \alpha \exp(-2Dq^2\tau) + \left(\frac{\gamma}{\langle N_{cv} \rangle}\right) \left(\frac{4D\tau}{w^2}\right)^{-3/2} \quad (1)$$

In (1), τ is the time delay; $D = k_B T / (3\pi\eta d)$ is the Stokes–Einstein diffusion coefficient, where k_B is the Boltzmann's constant, T is the absolute temperature, η is the viscosity of the suspending medium, and d is the particle diameter; $q = 4\pi n \sin(\theta/2)/\lambda_0$ is the magnitude of scattering

vector, where n is the refractive index of the suspending medium, θ the scattering angle ($\theta = \pi$ rad in our case), and λ_0 the free-space wavelength of incident light; α is an instrumental coherence factor (ideally, $\alpha = 1$); $\gamma = 2^{-3/2}$ is a constant associated with a Gaussian illumination profile, $\langle N_{cv} \rangle$ is the average number of particles in the coherence volume, and w is the radius of the illumination area (core radius of the optical fiber in our case, $w = 25 \mu\text{m}$).

Equation (1) is a standard expression to quantify the effects of PNF in DLS measurements [41], [42], which has been used at ultralow concentrations [43], [44], [45] and in situations where PNF dominates [46]. As can be noted, for a larger number of particles, the third term in (1) vanishes and $g^{(2)}(\tau)$ reduces to its usual form, where it is connected to the electric field autocorrelation function, $g^{(1)}(\tau)$, in a straightforward manner through Siegert's relation, $g^{(2)}(\tau) = 1 + \alpha |g^{(1)}(\tau)|^2$.

Accounting for PNF impacts two complementary timescales; in general, particles' diffusion determines the decay of $g^{(2)}(\tau)$ at shorter times, while PNF manifests at longer ones. Based on numerical calculations of (1), we determined that such time scales are far apart in our case (see Appendix). In fact, to fully appreciate the decay due to PNF, one needs to measure $g^{(2)}(\tau)$ for time delays $\tau > 10^2$ s, which would require long integration times. In the time scales of our experiments, PNF manifests in $g^{(2)}(\tau)$ as an excess background and an apparent slower decay, without significant alteration to its shape [47] (see Appendix). Therefore, because the exponential decay of $g^{(2)}(t)$ dominates, the main consequence of not compensating for PNF is an underestimation of the decay rate, $\Gamma = q^2 D$, which can lead to an overestimation of the hydrodynamic diameter, d_h (see Appendix), as previously reported [43], [44], [45].

Knowing the above, we proceeded to our analysis in terms of the power spectrum, $P(f)$, shown in Fig. 3(e)–(h), which is the Fourier counterpart of $g^{(2)}(\tau)$, by the Wiener–Khinchin theorem, and retrieves equivalent dynamic information of the sample, as detailed below. This representation is also convenient for characterizing the frequency content of broadband, random signals because it allows identifying different sources of noise in a relatively simple manner; for instance, the characteristic frequency dependence of Flicker noise (f^{-1}) and shot noise (f^0) can be appreciated in the background noise spectra of Fig. 3.

From Fig. 3(e)–(h), $P(f)$ overlap when measured at the same gain, $\xi = 1 \times 10^4$, confirming that I_s was kept constant in both architectures. Moreover, balanced CG-DLS makes $\xi = 3 \times 10^4$ accessible without saturating the detector, leading to $P(f)$ with larger amplitude. Importantly, this gain factor is the largest one available at the commercial detector we used; however, because the signal's baseline has been effectively removed, $I(t)$ is far from the saturation limit, and higher gain factors could be used, if available.

By the above-discussed dominance of the exponential decay of $g^{(2)}(t)$, $P(f)$ is expected to preserve its Lorentzian envelope, which is associated with Brownian particles diffusing normally in a Newtonian fluid [1]. In the double-logarithmic plots of Fig. 3(e)–(h), it can be visualized as the transition from a zero log-slope, at lower frequencies, toward an asymptotic log-slope of -2 at higher ones. In this spectral representation, the decay rate is encoded in the corner frequency of $P(f)$, $f_c = \Gamma/(2\pi)$. The experimental values of f_c are indicated in Fig. 3(e)–(h); for our experimental conditions

Fig. 4. Joint representation of temporal and spectral metrics for CG-DLS and balanced CG-DLS, at different concentrations and gains, as indicated.

(PS-100 nm particles, in water, at room temperature), the theoretical corner frequency is $f_c^0 \approx 450$ Hz.

As the concentration decreases, the envelope of $P(f)$ in CG-DLS distorts significantly [Fig. 3(g)] until it finally approaches the noise floor [Fig. 3(h)], compromising the reliability of the dynamic information that can be retrieved at the lower concentrations. In contrast, $P(f)$ measured with balanced CG-DLS also decreased in amplitude as the concentration decreased but maintained their Lorentzian shape at all concentrations, with the expected value of f_c , being influenced only by PNF, even at 10^{-7} vol/vol, where there are approximately ten NPs in the coherence volume.

The superior performance of balanced CG-DLS, from a signal standpoint, is further illustrated in Fig. 4, where we compared jointly the SNR, calculated as $\text{SNR} = 10 \log_{10}(\sigma/I)$, where σ is the standard deviation $I(t)$, and the area under $P(f)$, $\beta = \int P(f)df$, indicative of the energy in the scattering fluctuations. Markers of different shapes and colors correspond to the average of 2000 spectra, acquired for ten minutes, at different concentrations and gain factors, as indicated.

The representation of Fig. 4 allows analyzing the results from multiple perspectives. For instance, at the same gain (same marker color), the relationship between the temporal (SNR) and the spectral (β) metric reports a similar trend for all configurations, which means that the scattering contribution increases with concentration in a consistent manner, regardless of the apparatus used to measure. At the same concentration (same marker shape), the SNR is around 3 dB higher in balanced CG-DLS as compared to CG-DLS, when measured at the same gain. Then, when ξ is further increased from 1×10^4 to 3×10^4 in balanced CG-DLS, the SNR seems to remain constant but β increases by around one order of magnitude, indicating that $P(f)$ emerges more from the noise floor. Moreover, the SNR in balanced CG-DLS at the lowest concentration (red circle), is similar to that in CG-DLS at the highest one (blue star). The greatest benefit is evident at the lower concentrations (red triangle and circle), where $P(f)$ can be measured with balanced CG-DLS, but not with CG-DLS.

Fig. 5 shows d_h retrieved from $P(f)$ measured with CG-DLS and balanced CG-DLS, accounting for PNF. At each concentration, 2000 spectra were recorded over 10 min, with an integration time of 300 ms. The data points and error bars correspond to the mean and standard deviation, respectively, that result from processing all spectra. For reference, the tolerance range determined by the manufacturer is shaded.

As mentioned above, complementary measurements of particle size were performed independently with two

Fig. 5. Hydrodynamic diameter retrieved as a function of particle concentration with CG-DLS, balanced CG-DLS, and two commercial DLS instruments. The number of particles is indicated, considering the measurement volume in each case. See text for details.

commercial DLS equipment (DLS 1: Malvern Zetasizer Nano ZS ZEN5600; DLS 2: Anton Paar Litesizer DLS 700). These data points correspond to the mean and standard deviation of the particle size distribution, as retrieved by the equipment. These measurements are redundant, but we decided to include them because, surprisingly, both show large deviations of d_h at volume fractions where the effects of PNF should not be appreciable in their measurement volume, which is on the order of 1 nL, according to the manufacturer. In other words, in this equipment, the contribution of PNF should be negligible even at the lower concentrations due to the large values of $\langle N \rangle$ (see Appendix). Yet, d_h deviates significantly in both cases.

The repeatability of balanced CG-DLS was assessed by performing measurements on three different samples, at the lowest volume fraction of 10^{-7} , obtaining an inter-sample variability for f_c and d_h of 4.1% and 4.6%, respectively (see Appendix). Long-term stability of balanced CG-DLS was also assessed by performing one-hour-long measurements at the lower volume fractions, 10^{-6} and 10^{-7} . The measurements did not report increasing/decreasing trends, and the values of f_c exhibited approximately normal distributions around their mean, resulting in time variability of 8.6% and 5.1% for f_c and d_h , respectively, at volume fraction 10^{-6} ; and 14.9% and 3.8% for f_c and d_h , respectively, at volume fraction 10^{-7} (see Appendix).

In closing, we would like to point out that the detection of dynamic weak scattering has been the focus of several recent studies, where various experimental conditions have been explored, including different wavelengths and a variety of particle materials, concentrations, and sizes. Table I provides a summary of the main figures of merit from such studies; we included the experimental parameters reported by the authors and other quantities, derived from them, that we calculated to facilitate the comparison with the present work. Specifically, based on Mie theory [5], we calculated the backscattering cross section (σ_{bs}), and the product $\langle N \rangle \sigma_{bs}$, where $\langle N \rangle$ is the average number of particles, which is proportional to I_s in a situation of single scattering [1]. The latter allows us to compare our results from the perspective of a weak scattering signal, irrespective of whether it takes place either due to ultralow concentrations (small $\langle N \rangle$) or due to inefficient scattering (small σ_{bs}) which, in turn, can be due to small size parameters or low optical contrast. Interestingly, as can be noted in Table I, $I_s \propto \langle N \rangle \sigma_{bs}$, in our experimental conditions is comparable to that measured in molecular diffusion [48]. In fairness, measuring such fast dynamics requires a wide

TABLE I
SUMMARY OF WEAK-SCATTERING DLS

REF	YEAR	MAT	PARTICLE DIAMETER, d (NM)	λ_0 (NM)	CONCENTRATION (10^{-7} VOL/VOL)	$\langle N \rangle$	σ_{bs} (MM ²)	$I_s \propto \langle N \rangle \sigma_{bs}$
[43]	2021	PS	152	532	0.096 TO 0.77	6 TO 48	7.49×10^{-4}	4.49×10^{-3}
			693		9.1 TO 73	6 TO 48	2.07×10^{-2}	1.25×10^{-1}
[48]	2022	PEG	1.9	532	1.13×10^5	1.80×10^{11}	2.15×10^{-15}	3.87×10^{-4}
			1.9	488			2.93×10^{-15}	5.28×10^{-4}
			4.7	532			4.92×10^{-13}	8.84×10^{-2}
			4.7	488			6.71×10^{-13}	1.21×10^{-1}
			4.7	488			6.71×10^{-13}	1.21×10^{-1}
[45]	2023	PS	203	532	0.32 TO 2.5	9 TO 67	7.49×10^{-4}	8.57×10^{-3}
			693		9.1 TO 73	6 TO 48	2.07×10^{-2}	1.25×10^{-1}
[50]	2023	SiO ₂	103	532	7 TO 1,300	1,000	3.34×10^{-5}	3.33×10^{-2}
			113			780	5.20×10^{-5}	4.05×10^{-2}
			233			89	1.38×10^{-4}	1.22×10^{-2}
[51]	2023	Au	28	532	1 TO 3,600	5	4.32×10^{-5}	2.16×10^0
			488	1.79×10^{-5}		6.96×10^{-1}		
THIS WORK		PS	100	670	1 TO 1,000	12	5.48×10^{-5}	6.58×10^{-4}

frequency bandwidth, which consequently increases the noise. Therefore, verifying that balanced CG-DLS could be used to measure molecular diffusion is left for future work, encouraged by the current demonstration of its sensitivity to the signal levels required for such fine detection. As a side note, the reader should note that, in Table I, we are including only reports dealing with situations of ultra-weak scattering. We left out, for instance, reports on DLS-OCT, which operate at much higher concentrations [9], [10]; to the best of the authors' knowledge, their lower concentration limit to consider the suspension to be "extremely dilute" is around 5×10^{-5} vol/vol [46], which is practically the upper limit of our scale (see Fig. 5), and it can be as high as 3×10^{-1} vol/vol [49]. In Table I, PS, PEG, SiO₂, and Au stand for polystyrene, polyethylene glycol, silicon dioxide, and gold, respectively.

IV. CONCLUSION

In summary, we proposed an innovative optical sensing platform, which enables the detection of interferometrically amplified scattering signals in a background-free manner. The reasoning of our design is based on using two independent reference fields: one for interferometric amplification, in a low-coherence common-path architecture, and the other for baseline removal, in a scheme of balanced detection incorporated into a dual-path architecture. Our practical implementation is all-optical-fiber, hardware-undemanding, and based on general-purpose components.

Balanced detection has been employed in various contexts to extract weak signals from undesired strong backgrounds. Nevertheless, to the best of our knowledge, this is the first time it is used in a situation where the background is part of the signal of interest, since the reference field that is to be removed was purposely generated for the interferometric amplification of scattering.

Moreover, CG-DLS is especially suited for situations involving samples with high concentrations of particulates, thanks to its powerful optical isolation of single scattering from optically dense environments (picoliter-sized coherence volume) [17]. It has been used, for instance, on concentrated suspensions of PS NPs up to 1×10^{-1} vol/vol [17], [19], and even on whole blood at physiological hematocrit [20], [21]. This attribute is preserved in balanced CG-DLS; therefore,

Fig. 6. Power delivered to the sample as a function of the light level of the superluminescent diode (SLD), with both ends in air. The red and gray markers represent the sample and the background, respectively, in the balanced CG-DLS configuration, while the blue points correspond to the traditional CG-DLS architecture. The dashed lines indicate the equivalent power level in both architectures.

our results suggest that this new technique has the potential for sizing NPs across six decades of concentration.

Finally, in our proof-of-concept experiments, we demonstrated particle sizing at concentrations as low as 1×10^{-7} vol/vol. At this concentration, there are only about ten NPs in the coherence volume, and the strength of the scattering signal is comparable to that reported in experiments of molecular diffusion. This not only reveals the high sensitivity of balanced CG-DLS but also encourages its use in other weak-scattering scenarios where only a handful of NPs are available for measurements.

APPENDIX

Fig. 6 shows the optical power measured at the sample port, i.e., the power delivered to the sample, with permutation G (see Fig. 2), as a function of the intensity level of the light source. Based on this characterization, one can adjust accordingly to ensure that the magnitude of the incident light, and consequently that of I_r and I_s , are kept constant in both setups. For instance, if one desires to set the incident power at 1.5 mW, the source level needs to be set at 600 and 950 for CG-DLS and balanced CG-DLS, respectively.

Fig. 7(a) shows the intensity autocorrelation function [I-ACF, $g^{(2)}(\tau)$], for our experimental conditions, where PNF are accounted for based on the standard approximation of an illuminating finite Gaussian beam [(1)] [41], [42]. In our experiments, PNF manifests as an excess background (main figure) and an apparently slower decay of $g^{(2)}(\tau)$ (inset), which leads to an overestimation of d_h , as shown in Fig. 7(b).

The repeatability of balanced CG-DLS was assessed by performing three independent measurements on different days, using a different sample each day, at the lowest volume fraction of 10^{-7} , obtaining the following results: day 1: $f_c = 322 \pm 23$ Hz, $d_h = 119 \pm 8$ nm; day 2: $f_c = 297 \pm 19$ Hz, $d_h = 131 \pm 6$ nm; day 3: $f_c = 308 \pm 31$ Hz, $d_h = 126 \pm 5$ nm. Based on the average values, the inter-sample variability for f_c and d_h is 4.1% and 4.6%, respectively, revealing that the measurement is repeatable.

The long-term stability of balanced CG-DLS was also assessed, by performing one hour-long measurements at the lower volume fractions, 10^{-6} and 10^{-7} , as shown in Fig. 8. The measurements are stable over time, without increasing/decreasing trends, and f_c exhibits approximately normal distributions around their mean, as shown in the inset of Fig. 8. For volume fraction 10^{-6} the results were $f_c = 370 \pm 32$ Hz

Fig. 7. Effects of PNF on $g^{(2)}(\tau)$ and d_h . (a) $g^{(2)}(\tau)$, normalized to its maximum asymptotic value at $\tau \rightarrow 0$, for different values of $\langle N \rangle$, as indicated. The inset highlights the apparently slower decay rate of $g^{(2)}(\tau)$; for reference, the $(1/e)$ criterion is marked. (b) Ratio of d_h , retrieved from $g^{(2)}(\tau)$, to the nominal size.

Fig. 8. Long-term stability of balanced CG-DLS, following f_c over time at the lower volume fractions, 10^{-6} and 10^{-7} . The inset shows the corresponding histogram of the data points in the main plot.

and $d_h = 118 \pm 6$ nm, resulting in long term variability of 8.6% and 5.1% for f_c and d_h , respectively; while for volume fraction 10^{-7} the results were $f_c = 307 \pm 46$ Hz and $d_h = 129 \pm 5$ nm, resulting in long term variability of variability 14.9% and 3.8% for f_c and d_h , respectively.

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